

POWER QUALITY ENHANCEMENT IN DISTRIBUTION GRID USING DSTATCOM

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ABSTRACT

D-STATCOM is used to regulate reactive power in distribution networks, where inductive loads require more reactive power, reducing the power factor and limiting active power flow. This research develops a D-STATCOM using a voltage source converter to inject reactive power into distribution lines, converting output voltage to system voltage to manage VAR generation. To ensure quality power at the load bus, employing FACTS devices like D-STATCOM is essential. Positioned close to the load bus, D-STATCOM compensates for the high reactive power demand, preventing RMS voltage drops. It also addresses load balancing, neutral current compensation, reactive power imbalances, and harmonic mitigation, maintaining steady voltage despite load changes. Extensive simulations using MATLAB/Simulink demonstrate its effectiveness under various conditions.

Keywords: DSTATCOM, Reactive Power, VSI, VAR, PI Controller, Power Quality, Voltage Stability, Reactive Power Compensation

I. INTRODUCTION

FACTS devices provide quick and reliable control over transmission parameters like voltage, phase angle, and line impedance, enhancing power quality in low voltage distribution systems[1]. Custom power devices such as D-STATCOM, UPQC, and DVR share similarities with FACTS devices. Among these, D-STATCOM is notable for its cost-effective reactive power compensation. FACTS devices maintain dynamic stability and power quality by adjusting impedance, phase angle, and voltage[2]. This work focuses on the Distributed Static Compensator (D-STATCOM), a shunt-connected power electronic device fed by a voltage source. D-STATCOM reduces harmonics and other power quality issues. Its performance depends on control techniques that extract reference currents and supply pulses to the VSI's gate terminals. A review of various D-

STATCOM studies highlights its effectiveness. Under various operating conditions, a shunt-connected device like D-STATCOM provides reliable power and enhances stability. It supports voltage during low supply situations, such as sags, improving power quality at the load bus. D-STATCOM is widely used in distribution systems for reactive power compensation with appropriate control strategies[3]. Its popularity stems from being an affordable and easy-to-use solution for enhancing electricity quality at loads.

II. POWER QUALITY PROBLEMS

Power quality (PQ) issues are widespread today due to the increased use of electronic devices like IT equipment, power electronics, variable-speed drives (VSDs), programmable logic controllers (PLCs), and energy-efficient lighting. These non-linear loads cause and suffer from PQ problems, disrupting voltage waveforms. Voltage sags, swells, and transients are common issues that affect sensitive equipment, leading to malfunction or damage. Harmonic distortions further degrade the power quality, causing additional losses and reducing the efficiency of electrical systems. Mitigating these PQ problems is crucial for ensuring the reliability and longevity of modern electronic devices and industrial equipment.

Figure 1: Pie-chart of Power Quality problems

Various factors such as intermittent transient surges, surges/spikes, flicker, uncontrolled voltages, damping/attenuation, interruptions, and waveform disturbances (e.g., power factor, harmonics) can impact electrical equipment.

Figure 2: Power quality problems

III. HARMONIC DISTORTION:

Adding non-linear loads to power systems often leads to one of the most prevalent power quality

issues: harmonics. This can result in equipment failure, overheating, improper load tripping, malfunctioning protective relays, and communication circuit issues.

Conventional electricity pricing criteria such as active power, reactive power, and power factor cannot accurately determine harmonic power flow. In non-sinusoidal conditions, these criteria lose their relevance as they are defined for sinusoidal situations. Instead, a new metric called reactive apparent power becomes crucial. Harmonics not only increase system losses but also fail to deliver net energy to the load. Devices generating harmonics are ubiquitous in households, service sectors, and industries. Harmonics stem from non-linear loads, where the current shape changes concerning the applied voltage. Common non-linear load examples include power electronics like rectifiers, inverters, electronic starters, frequency converter motors, switching power supplies, and discharge lights. Activation of non-linear loads initiates the circulation of Total Harmonic Distortion Currents (THDI)[4].

Consequences:

- i. Deviations from sinusoidal voltages can pose operational challenges for electronic power control systems.
- ii. Electronic signaling systems, designed for low currents, are susceptible to interference from high-frequency electromagnetic fields.
- iii. Elevated risk of resonance occurrence.
- iv. Overloading of neutral in three-phase systems.
- v. Overheating of wires and devices, leading to potential electrical equipment failure.

Figure 3: Harmonic Distortion

IV. OVER VOLTAGE:

An overvoltage occurs when voltage exceeds normal levels for more than 10 milliseconds. Disconnection of large loads (such as industrial production processes), or natural events like lightning, can trigger overvoltage's. Unlike spikes and transients, power surges have greater magnitude and shorter duration. Abrupt energy bursts from power surges can result in memory loss, data corruption, and damage to processors or circuit boards.

Causes:

Lightning strikes, power factor adjustment capacitors or line switches, and disconnection of large loads.

Consequences:

Damage to components (especially electronic parts) and insulating materials, data processing errors, and electromagnetic interference.

Figure 4 Voltage Sag

Over Voltage Swells/Voltage Surges:

A brief increase in voltage at the power frequency lasting more than a few seconds, typically extending beyond one cycle, surpassing normal limits. Explore our range of surge protectors to shield your application from the main power supply entry to the end-load connection point. Surge protective devices (SPDs) are designed to endure transients and surges.

Causes:

Swells may arise from starting and stopping large loads, inadequately sized power sources, and poorly regulated transformers, especially during off-peak periods.

Effects:

Potential consequences of swells include data loss, flickering lights and displays[2], equipment damage or malfunction due to excessive voltage, and more.

Voltage Spikes and Transients:

Rapid, high-energy bursts superimposed on a standard mains power supply, lasting only milliseconds, are termed transients and spikes. They result from the sudden release of stored energy and can vary in voltage from a few volts to several thousand volts, with some reaching 6 kV or more. Transients and spikes are common during electrical storms and following lightning strikes.

Unlike power surges, spikes and transients have a shorter duration and higher magnitude. These abrupt energy bursts can lead to memory loss, data corruption, and damage to processors or circuit boards[5].

Voltage Sag:

Figure 5: Voltage Sag

Voltage sag is a brief (lasting between 0.5 and 60 cycles) decrease in the RMS voltage magnitude, typically resulting from a malfunction in the power system. Voltage sags pose a significant power quality challenge for many industrial clients, especially those with critical processes, as they can disrupt operations. When voltage drops below 90% of the nominal value, it is classified as sag.

Causes:

- i. Faults in the distribution or transmission network, often involving parallel feeds.
- ii. Issues with the customer's installation.
- iii. Activation of heavy loads and starting large motors.
- iv. Deactivation of a significant source of reactive power.
- v. Functions of surge suppressors within the power system.

Interruptions:

Interruptions occur when a protective device on the source side opens a circuit section due to a fault condition. These disruptions can be brief or prolonged. Momentary interruptions typically last a few seconds, while sustained interruptions can persist for minutes or even hours.

Causes (Short Interruption):

Primarily caused by automatic activation of protective mechanisms to isolate faulty sections of the network. Common sources of faults include insulator flashover, lightning, and insulation failure.

Consequences:

Loss of information, breakdown of data processing equipment, and tripping of protective devices. Sensitive equipment like PCs, ASDs, and PLCs may shut down if they are not equipped to handle the situation.

Causes (Long Interruption):

Events such as equipment failure in the power system network, storms, damage to electricity wires or poles by animals or objects (such as trees or vehicles), fire, human error, improper coordination, or malfunctioning protective measures.

Consequences:

System shutdown.

Power Quality Improvement: DSTATCOM

Power distribution networks utilize Distribution Static Compensators (DSTATCOMs), specialized power electronic devices enhancing system reliability and quality. They address various power quality issues arising from distributed energy resources and non-linear loads. Key attributes include[6]:

1. Voltage Regulation:

DSTATCOM monitors network voltage at the connection point, swiftly injecting or absorbing reactive power to maintain voltage within predefined limits. This ensures a stable power supply, safeguarding sensitive equipment.

2. Harmonics Mitigation:

By filtering out harmonic currents and voltages, DSTATCOM reduces power waveform distortion caused by unwanted high-frequency impulses, enhancing system efficiency.

3. Reactive Power Compensation:

Supplying or absorbing reactive power optimizes the power factor, reducing losses and grid pressure, enhancing overall system efficiency.

4. Flicker Reduction:

DSTATCOM minimizes voltage fluctuations caused by load changes or grid disruptions, improving power quality and protecting equipment.

5. Load Balancing:

By distributing reactive power among feeders, DSTATCOM reduces overloading and enhances distribution system performance.

6. Fault Current Limiting:

During short-circuit events, DSTATCOM limits fault currents, enhancing network safety and protection. DSTATCOMs, equipped with advanced power electronics like control algorithms and IGBTs, continuously monitor and adjust grid conditions to maintain stability and quality. Their adoption benefits utilities and customers, ensuring a reliable, efficient distribution system that meets quality standards while reducing equipment replacement and maintenance costs. Additionally, they provide critical support during grid disturbances by quickly responding to fault conditions. As grids evolve with renewable energy integration, DSTATCOMs play a vital role in sustaining a high-quality power supply. Their ability to manage and mitigate fault currents is essential for maintaining system integrity and preventing widespread outages.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Following are the waveform results shown for the comparison of reactive power with and without STATCOM. There are two scenarios of reactive power:

1. If the reactive power is more than the requirement then it will get absorbed, And
2. If the reactive power is less than the requirement then it will provide the power.
3. So, depending upon the reactive power, STATCOM works.

VOLTAGE AND CURRENT:

Figure 6: Voltage (Vabc) and Current (Iabc) at Grid

The figure 6 illustrates the voltage and current on the Grid side of an electrical system. It shows the waveform and amplitude of both voltage and current over time, potentially including phase information. The context pertains to the electricity grid, indicating where power is delivered or drawn, and includes units like volts for voltage and amperes for current. This visual helps analyze power transfer efficiency, power quality, and the overall health of the grid connection[7].

DC BUS VOLTAGE:

Figure 7: DC link Voltage (Vdc)

The figure illustrates the DC bus voltage in an electrical system. It displays the voltage level and possibly its variation over time. The context pertains to the DC bus, which is a central component in many power electronic systems, such as inverters. Understanding the DC bus voltage is crucial for ensuring stable operation and proper control of these systems. The visual representation may include units such as volts for voltage and annotations indicating key points or thresholds for safe operation. At $t=0$, Circuit breaker is closed i.e. DTSTACOM is connected in circuit. And at $t=0$, at starting inrush current is present upto 0.3ms. At $t=0.3$, DSTATCOM is disconnected and reactive power is increased.

VI. INVERTER AND LOAD CURRENT:

Figure 7: Current at inverter and load (Iinv, Iload)

The figure 7, illustrates the current at the inverter and load in an electrical system. It displays the current levels and potentially their variation over time. This information is crucial for monitoring and controlling power flow within the system. Understanding the currents at both the inverter and load helps ensure efficient operation, prevent overloading, and maintain system stability. The visual representation may include units such as amperes for current and annotations indicating key points or thresholds for safe operation.

GRID’S ACTIVE AND REACTIVE POWER:

Figure 8: Active and Reactive Power of Grid

The figure 8 illustrates the active and reactive power of the grid in an electrical system. It displays both the active power, which represents real power transferred to or from the grid, and the reactive power, which represents the exchange of reactive energy. Understanding these parameters is essential for grid management, as they affect the efficiency, stability, and voltage regulation of the system. The visual representation may include units such as kilowatts for active power and Volt-amperes reactive (VAR) for reactive power, along with annotations indicating key points or thresholds for grid operation[8-12].

At $t=0$, Circuit breaker is closed i.e. DTSTACOM is connected in circuit. And at $t=0$, at starting inrush current is present upto 0.3ms. At $t=0.3$, DSTATCOM is disconnected and reactive power is increased and no change in Active power.

INVERTER’S ACTIVE AND REACTIVE POWER:

Figure 9: Active and Reactive Power at Inverter Side

The figure 9 illustrates the active and reactive power at the inverter side in an electrical system. It displays both the active power, which represents the real power converted by the inverter, and the reactive power, which indicates the exchange of reactive energy. Understanding these parameters is crucial for controlling the inverter's operation, ensuring efficient power conversion, and maintaining grid stability. The visual representation may include units such as kilowatts for active power and Volt-amperes reactive (VAR) for reactive power, along with annotations indicating key points or thresholds for safe and optimal inverter performance[13-15].

At $t=0$, Circuit breaker is closed i.e. DTSTACOM is connected in circuit. And at $t=0$, starting inrush current is present up to 20 ms. When DSTATCOM is disconnected and reactive power oscillates near zero.

LOAD’S ACTIVE AND REACTIVE POWER:

Figure 10: Active and Reactive Power at Load Side

Figure 10 illustrates the active and reactive power at the load side in an electrical system. It displays both the active power, which represents the real power consumed by the load, and the reactive power, which indicates the exchange of reactive energy with the load. Understanding these parameters is essential for evaluating load performance, ensuring efficient power consumption, and maintaining system stability. The visual representation includes units such as kilowatts for active power and volt- amperes reactive (VAR) for reactive power, along with annotations highlighting key points or thresholds for safe and efficient load operation.

At $t=0$, Circuit breaker is closed i.e. DTSTACOM is connected in circuit. And at $t=0$, at starting inrush current is present up to 170 ms. When DSTATCOM is disconnected and it will remain stable up to 300 ms. At $t=300$, DSTATCOM is disconnected due to opening action of circuit breaker. And reactive power changes slightly.

VII. TESTING AND CONCLUSION

Following figure shows the measurement and testing of both the active and reactive power with and without STATCOM for the comparison purpose.

Table 1: Measured Active and Reactive Power D-STATCOM

Sr. No.	Volage and Current	Active Power (P)	Reactive Power (Q)
1	Vabc	1.999×10^5	0
	Iabc	0	9.996×10^4
2	Vabc	9294	0
	Iinv	0	2.701×10^4
3	Vabc	1.999×10^5	0
	Iload	0	9.996×10^4

Figure 11: Active and Reactive power measurements

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper has explored the mathematical model, performance characteristics, and technical design of DSTATCOM. The research validated the device's effectiveness when sensitive loads are connected to the grid, producing satisfactory results. Its rapid response time and advanced control behavior have proven effective in reducing harmonic distortion. Both tabulated and simulated results demonstrate the proposed controller's superiority over traditional ones, ensuring efficient operation of the local distribution grid with sensitive loads. This work focused on the source of disturbances from the generation perspective. Reducing the harmonic value of currents at the source side significantly improves overall harmonic distortion, resulting in a better waveform profile for both voltage and current. The fourth leg of the VSC effectively reduces the neutral current flow caused by imbalanced loads.

IX. FUTURE SCOPE

There are several ways to expand upon the project work detailed in this report. Some potential directions include:

1. DSTATCOM as a FACTS Device: DSTATCOM belongs to the broader category of Flexible AC Transmission System (FACTS) devices. It addresses issues in distribution networks related to reactive power imbalances, harmonic distortion, and voltage fluctuations.

2. Basic Operation of DSTATCOM: To mitigate voltage fluctuations, harmonic distortions, and other power quality problems in distribution networks, a DSTATCOM measures voltage and power quality parameters, compares them to reference values, and uses power electronics to inject or absorb reactive power as needed. This process helps enhance the overall performance, stability, and reliability of distribution networks.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. B. Pandu et al., "Power Quality Enhancement in Sensitive Local Distribution Grid Using Interval Type-II Fuzzy Logic Controlled DSTATCOM," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 59888- 59899, 2021, doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3072865.
- [2] J.P. Sen, K. P. Panda and S. Rout, "Enhancement of power quality and voltage flicker mitigation using new PWM based DSTATCOM," 2017 International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS), Madurai, India, 2017, pp. 350-355, doi: 10.1109/ICCONS.2017.8250741.
- [3] K. Chenchireddy, V. Kumar, K. R. Sreejyothi and P. Tejaswi, "A Review on D-STATCOM Control Techniques for Power Quality Improvement in Distribution," 2021 5th International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA), Coimbatore, India, 2021, pp. 201-208, doi: 10.1109/ICECA52323.2021.9676019.
- [4] B. Singh, P. Jayaprakash, D. P. Kothari, A. Chandra and K. A. Haddad, "Comprehensive Study of DSTATCOM Configurations," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 854-870, May 2014, doi: 10.1109/TII.2014.2308437.
- [5] S. R. Arya, B. Singh, R. Niwas, A. Chandra and K. Al- Haddad, "Power Quality Enhancement Using DSTATCOM in Distributed Power Generation System," in *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 52, no. 6, pp. 5203-5212, Nov.-Dec. 2016, doi:10.1109/TIA.2016.2600644.
- [6] T. Jacob and L. P. Suresh, "A review paper on the elimination of harmonics in multilevel inverters using bioinspired algorithms," 2016 International Conference on Circuit, Power and Computing Technologies (ICCPCT), Nagercoil, India, 2016, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/ICCPCT.2016.7530273.
- [7] Zhou, W. Zhong, Y. Ma, K. Guo, J. Yin and C. Wei, "Control Strategy Research of DSTATCOM Using Active Disturbance Rejection Control Based on Total Disturbance Error Compensation," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 50138- 50150, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3069293.

- [8] K. Swetha and V. Sivachidambaranathan, "Reactive Power Control and Harmonic Mitigation by using DSTATCOM with Different Controllers," 2019 3rd International conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA), Coimbatore, India, 2019, pp. 490-496, doi: 10.1109/ICECA.2019.8822160.
- [9] Lucas do Nascimento Gomes , Armando José Gomes Abrantes-Ferreira, "Synchronverter-Based STATCOM With Voltage Imbalance Compensation Functionality," IEEE Transactions On Industrial Electronics, Vol. 69, No. 5, MaY 2022, pp. 4836 – 4844
- [10] Ehsan Hashemzadeh , Mohammadreza Aghamohammadi, "Secondary Control for a D-STATCOM DC-Link Voltage Under Capacitance Degradation," IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON POWER ELECTRONICS, VOL. 36, NO. 11, NOVEMBER 2021, pp 13215-13224
- [11] Li Wang , Wei-Sheng Liu, Chuan-Chieh Yeh, "Reduction of Three-Phase Voltage Unbalance Subject to Special Winding Connections of Two Single-Phase Distribution Transformers of a Microgrid System Using a Designed D-STATCOM Controller," IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INDUSTRY APPLICATIONS, VOL. 54, NO. 3, MAY/JUNE 20, pp. 2002-2010
- [12] Xuefeng Wang and Li Peng, "Dynamic Voltage Equalization Control of D-STATCOM Under Unbalanced Grid Faults in a Low-Voltage Network", IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON POWER ELECTRONICS, VOL. 38, NO. 2, FEBRUARY 2023, pp. 2384-2397
- [13] Ahmed Y. Hatata, Eman. O. Hasan, Mohammed A. Alghassab, "Centralized Control Method for Voltage Coordination Challenges With OLTC and D-STATCOM in Smart Distribution Networks Based IoT Communication Protocol," IEEE Access, VOL. 11, 2023, pp. 11903-11922
- [14] Jong Ha Woo, Lei Wu, "D-STATCOM d-q Axis Current Reference Control Applying DDPG Algorithm in the Distribution System," IEEE Access, VOL.09, 2021, pp. 145840-145851
- [15] Eklas Hossain, Mehmet Rida Tür, "Analysis and Mitigation of Power Quality Issues in Distributed Generation Systems Using Custom Power Devices," IEEE Access, VOL. 6, 2018, pp.16816-16833